

Resonance fluorescence studies of spectroscopically pure SiO₂

Fuat Bayrakceken^a, Ali Yaman^{b*} and Behzad B. Jomehri^c

^aYeditepe University, Department of Electric and Electronics Engineering, Uskudar 81160, Istanbul, Turkey

^bAnkara University, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Physics, Tandogan, 06100 Ankara, Turkey
E-mail : ayaman@science.ankara.edu.tr

^cAnkara University, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Engineering Physics, 06100 Tandogan, Ankara, Turkey

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Resonance fluorescence has been observed for spectroscopically pure SiO₂, at 288.2 nm by high power optical pumping, using flash photolysis technique. Absorption and emission bands are recorded photographically in the UV-region. Absorption and emission bands are observed without fine structure at room temperature.

When a beam of light is passed through a transparent substance, a small amount of the radiation is scattered, the scattering persisting even if all dust particles or other extraneous matter are rigorously excluded from the substance. If monochromatic radiation, or radiation of a very narrow frequency gap, is used, the scattered radiation will consist almost entirely the incident frequency (Rayleigh scattering) but, in addition, certain discrete frequencies above and below that of the incident beam will be scattered, it is this which is referred to as Raman scattering^{1,2}. Stokes' radiation is generally more intense than anti-Stokes'. In the case of hot molecules this phenomena can be reversed. Scattering with change of frequency originating, in essence, from a Doppler effect can also be observed with gases, liquids, and solids³.

Scattering of radiation without change of frequency can also arise from larger scattering centres like dust particles, and is generally referred to as Mie scattering⁴. Since such scattering can be very intense, it is very rarely totally absent unless extraordinary efforts are made to remove dust and other Mie scatterers from the system. Akimov *et al.*⁵, observed experimentally, the strong effect of heat pulses on the intensity of the luminescence of free and bound excitons, created by optical illumination of the silicon surface. Hayashi and Yamamoto⁶, studied the optical properties of SiO₂ films in relation to embedded Si mesoscopic particles. They observed red luminescence peak analogous to that of porous 'Si' in films containing 'Si' clusters rather than nanocrystals. They also observed Raman signals for the samples not due to the vibrational modes of Si-O-Si bands in SiO₂. It is well known that the Raman spectrum of amorphous SiO₂ exhibits a broad feature extending from about 50 to 600 cm⁻¹ with a pronounced peak around 420

cm⁻¹. Fukui *et al.*^{7,8}, studied the detection of adsorbed species on a SiO₂ surface by reflection absorption infrared spectroscopy. They investigated 50 nm SiO₂ layer deposited on the SiO₂/W/Si system. Such a SiO₂ layer can be considered thick enough to show the chemical nature of SiO₂ and avoid thermal diffusion of 'W' to the surface at reaction conditions. Transmission IR spectra of SiO₂ powder, such as Aerosil silica, showed that the surface of SiO₂ was covered with hydroxyl groups and physisorbed water. Zn₂SiO₄.SiO₂ materials were synthesized by Su *et al.*⁹ Photoluminescence emission bands and photoluminescence decay of this material were observed.

This study will lead us to understand how to make a visible blind UV-detector and other type of sensors.

Results and Discussion

Absorption of ultraviolet light raises the molecule (SiO₂) from the ground state to first excited state (S₁). At room temperature most molecules are in the lowest vibrational level of the ground state and it is from here that upward transitions by absorption of light take place. For SiO₂ molecule, the pattern of vibrational levels is not complex; therefore, all the transitions at around 288.2 nm appear as one narrow band ($\Delta\lambda \cong 0.25$ nm). After optical pumping to SiO₂ at 288.2 nm, the excited state (S₁) of the molecule can return to any vibrational, rotational energy levels of the ground state by emitting light as prompt or resonance fluorescence or Raman scattering results. In this particular case, if the emissions are coming from excited SiO₂ as Stokes and anti-Stokes bands, we should observe broad fluorescence bands. As it is seen from Fig. 1, absorption and emission bandwidths are same within experimental

error. Therefore, this emission is named as resonance fluorescence; there is no frequency difference or frequency shift in the absorption and emission spectra, both appeared at 288.2 nm. Fig. 1 shows the absorption and resonance fluorescence spectra on the photographic plate and enlarged microdensitometer traces of the absorption and resonance fluorescence. Inside the optical pumping cavity the temperature was little higher than the room temperature due to the high power flash lamps. During the optical pumping the flash lamps are also hot and emit some IR radiation but this radiation does not affect the absorption or emission spectra.

Fig. 1. (a) Absorption spectrum of spectroscopically pure SiO₂ at 288.2 nm; (b) resonance fluorescence spectrum of SiO₂ at 288.2 nm; (c) enlarged microdensitometer trace of the absorption spectrum of spectroscopically pure SiO₂ at low power optical pumping ($I \approx 10^3$ photon/pulse); (d) enlarged microdensitometer trace of the absorption spectrum of spectroscopically pure SiO₂ at high power optical pumping ($I \approx 10^{10}$ photon/pulse); (e) enlarged microdensitometer trace of the resonance fluorescence spectrum of SiO₂.

In this work, we observed the population inversion as resonance fluorescence, for the very first time, at 282.2 nm. This observation shows that there is a possibility to

manufacture a device which can emit a very narrow band coherent emission for SiO₂. Another possibility to construct a device, is visible blind UV-detector as a sensor. Next step will be the hole-burning experiments for the absorption band of SiO₂ at 282.2 nm. If the hole-burning experiments are successful, we may get the narrowest fluorescence line in the UV-region.

Experimental

Spectroscopically pure SiO₂ (spectrosilica grade) material was chosen as a sample for luminescence studies. SiO₂ was excited with a flash photolysis set-up consisting of two-parallel photo-tubes arranged in series, contained in a reflector (front surface mirror, reflecting 200–700 nm band of electromagnetic radiation), and the cavity was flushed with nitrogen to get rid of paramagnetic oxygen in the optical pumping system. The photoflash energies used were 780–1125 J, and the flash duration time was 2 μ s. Spectra were recorded on a Hilger medium quartz spectrograph, slit-width 0.025 mm; Ilford XK fast blue sensitive plates sensitised with sodium salicylate for UV recordings were developed in Ilford PQ universal developer. The spectra were photometered on a Joyce-Loebel MKIIB double beam recording microdensitometer. All spectroscopic recordings were carried out for single flashes.

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